

NFDI₄Chem

Smart+Clue

The NFDI4Chem Guessing Game

The card game *SmartClue* is brought to you by NFDI4Chem which is the chemistry consortium within the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) in Germany. Find out everything about NFDI4Chem at nfdi4chem.de.

SmartClue is based on our open educational resource (OER) 'FAIR Chemistry Data: A Research Data Management Workshop Concept'. Scan the QR code to directly access our OER publication.

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Smart+Clue

How to play?

NFDI4Chem presents its research data management (RDM) guessing game **SmartClue**, featuring general and chemistry-specific terms. The game encourages researchers to engage with RDM in a fun way.

Shuffle the cards and place them face down between the players. The first player draws a card and tries to explain the term on it without mentioning the term or any parts of it. Once the other players have correctly guessed the term, the next player draws a card. To increase the difficulty, skipping cards is not allowed! If several teams are playing against each other, set a time limit of 10 minutes. After this time, the team with the most guessed cards wins.

Have fun!

SmartClue

Data Life Cycle

M01

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ENHANCE
YOUR
DATA.

SmartClue

Open Science

M01

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ENHANCE
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DATA.

FAIR principles

M01

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DATA.

SmartClue

Good Research Practice

M01

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DATA.

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Research Data

M01

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DATA.

Copyright

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DATA.

Reproducible

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Data Management Plan

M01

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DATA.

Software Management Plan

M01

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DATA.

Open Access

M01

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YOUR
DATA.

Policy

M01

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DATA.

SmartClue

Coffee break

M01

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ENHANCE
YOUR
DATA.

RDMO

M01

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ENHANCE
YOUR
DATA.

Raw Data

M01

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ENHANCE
YOUR
DATA.

Funder

M01

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ENHANCE
YOUR
DATA.

SmartClue

Open Peer Review

M01

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ENHANCE
YOUR
DATA.

DFG

M01

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DATA.

Licence

M01

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Creative Commons

M01

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Metadata

MO2

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Tag

MO2

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Folder Structure

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Machine-readable

MO2

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DATA.

SMILES

MO2

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YOUR
DATA.

SmartClue

InChI

MO2

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DATA.

Chemical Identifier

MO2

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Ontology

MO2

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Controlled Vocabulary

MO2

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Standard

M02

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DATA.

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File Naming Convention

MO2

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ENHANCE
YOUR
DATA.

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README File

MO2

NFDI₄Chem

ENHANCE
YOUR
DATA.

SmartClue

Minimum Information

MO2

NFDI₄Chem

ENHANCE
YOUR
DATA.

PubChem

MO2

NFDI₄Chem

ENHANCE
YOUR
DATA.

SmartClue

Metadata Schema

MO2

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DATA.

Template

M03

NFDI₄Chem

ENHANCE
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DATA.

eLabFTW

M03

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ENHANCE
YOUR
DATA.

Chemotion ELN

M03

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ENHANCE
YOUR
DATA.

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Electronic Laboratory Notebook (ELN)

M03

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ENHANCE
YOUR
DATA.

ELN Finder

M03

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YOUR
DATA.

Open Source

M03

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ENHANCE
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Structure Editor

M03

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Documentation

M03

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Publication

M04

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Repository

M04

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Persistent Identifier

M04

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Backup

M04

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Archive

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Versioning

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Git

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Jupyter Notebooks

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DOI

M04

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ORCID

M04

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SmartClue

Data Availability Statement

M04

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ENHANCE
YOUR
DATA.

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RADAR4Chem

M04

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ENHANCE
YOUR
DATA.

3-2-1 Rule

M04

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Findable

M04

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YOUR
DATA.

Accessible

M04

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Interoperable

M04

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Reusable

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Data Journal

M04

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DATA.